

Study of Corrected QT Interval during Hypoglycemic Episodes in Diabetes Mellitus Subjects in a Tertiary Care Hospital MysuruRakesh V¹, Suneetha D K²¹Postgraduate, Department of General Medicine, Mysore medical college and Research Institute²Professor, Department of General Medicine, Mysore medical college and Research Institute

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Diabetes-related deaths frequently stem from cardiovascular issues, with diabetics facing higher QTc prolongation and a 2–10 fold increased risk of sudden cardiac death. Hypoglycemia, a severe diabetes complication, is linked to QT interval prolongation, heightening arrhythmia and mortality risks. This study will evaluate QTc during hypoglycemia in diabetic patients and its correlation with blood sugar levels and hypoglycemia severity.

Objectives: 1. To Study corrected QT interval during hypoglycemic episodes in diabetes mellitus subjects. 2. To Correlate QTc interval in relation to in-hospital mortality.

Materials and Methods: This study involved 80 diabetic patients admitted with severe hypoglycemia at K.R. Hospital, Mysuru. ECGs were recorded during hypoglycemic episodes, and QTc was calculated using the Bazett formula. Data were analyzed based on sex, type of diabetes, duration of diabetes, severity of hypoglycemia, and electrolyte levels.

Results: Out of 80 subjects, 55% were male, and 45% were female; 16.3% had Type 1 diabetes and 83.8% had Type 2 diabetes. QTc prolongation was significantly more common in females with severe hypoglycemia (RBS <54 mg/dL) compared to less severe cases (RBS <70 mg/dL). However, no significant association was found between QTc and RBS levels among male subjects. Mortality rates were higher in the severe hypoglycemia group.

Conclusion: In conclusion, this study shows that diabetic patients experiencing hypoglycemia have a significantly prolonged QTc interval. Additionally, the extent of QTc prolongation correlates with hypoglycemia severity, and a significantly prolonged mean QTc interval is observed in cases of in-hospital mortality.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus; Cardiovascular Complications; Corrected QT Interval (QTc); Hypoglycemia; Electrocardiogram (ECG); Random Blood Sugar Levels.

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Introduction

Diabetes-related deaths are primarily due to cardiovascular complications [1]. Early detection and treatment are crucial to reduce the high mortality associated with these complications in diabetes. QT prolongation on an electrocardiogram (ECG) is a common cardiac disorder that can lead to serious arrhythmias such as Torsade de Pointes. The QT interval measures the total time for ventricular depolarization and repolarization and is influenced by heart rate, thus the corrected QT interval (QTc) is used clinically [2].

While often seen in congenital conditions, QT prolongation can also result from various comorbidities and medications. Chronic inflammatory conditions, including diabetes, frequently exhibit QT prolongation [3]. Although its impact is generally mild in the broader

population, QT prolongation can significantly increase mortality risk in patients with existing cardiac issues. QTc prolongation has been shown to independently predict cardiovascular mortality in diabetics [4]. Given that cardiovascular disease is a common complication of diabetes, the effect of QT prolongation in these patients warrants attention.

Diabetics have a higher prevalence of QTc prolongation and face a 2–10 times greater risk of sudden cardiac death compared to the general population [5]. This increased prevalence is largely due to hyperglycemia and chronic myocardial changes. Hyperglycemia and coronary heart disease (CHD) are strong predictors of a prolonged QTc interval [6]. A population-based cross-sectional study found a high prevalence of QTc prolongation in diabetics, with CHD being independently

associated with it even after adjusting for age and sex [7]. Recent research identified female gender and treatment with insulin sensitizers as independent contributors to QTc prolongation [8,9]. Additionally, QTc independently predicts all-cause mortality in type 2 diabetics, with current HbA1c levels, long-term postprandial hyperglycemia, and higher glycemic variability being strong independent risk factors [10].

Besides hyperglycemia and cardiovascular disease, other diabetic complications and hypoglycemia are also linked to QTc prolongation. Baseline QTc interval significantly correlates with QTc prolongation during severe hypoglycemia in type 2 diabetics, and this prolongation is independent of serum potassium levels [11].

Other metabolic disorders like obesity, dyslipidemia, and hypertension are also risk factors for QTc prolongation in diabetics. Although many studies report associations between QTc prolongation and various risk factors and diabetic complications, results have been inconsistent [12,13]. Furthermore, there is a lack of studies on QTc prolongation in diabetics from the Indian region, where diabetes is highly prevalent. Therefore, this study aims to assess the prevalence of QT prolongation among diabetes mellitus subjects.

Objectives

1. To study the corrected QT interval during hypoglycemic episodes in diabetes mellitus subjects
2. To correlate QTc interval in relation to in-hospital mortality.

Methodology

Study design: Cross- Sectional Study

Study area: K.R. Hospital, Mysore Medical College and Research Institute, Mysuru

Study population: Patients attending Medical Emergency ward/ IPD of K.R. Hospital, MMC&RI

Selection of study subjects: This study was conducted in diabetic patients who are all admitted in medical ward with symptoms of severe hypoglycemia at K.R. Hospital, Mysuru.

Study Duration: 12 months.

Study period: August 2022 - July 2023.

Selection Criteria

Inclusion criteria: Diabetes mellitus patients above the age of 18years presenting with hypoglycemic episodes as per ADA guidelines (RBS<70mg/dl).

Exclusion criteria:

1. Alcoholics
2. Sepsis patients
3. Pregnancy
4. Patient diagnosed with insulinoma, insulin autoimmune hypoglycemia.
5. Patients with electrolyte abnormalities.
6. Coronary artery disease.
7. Concurrent use of drugs which causing Q-T prolongation (quinidine, procainamide, Tri & Tetra cyclic antidepressant).

Sampling Method: Simple random sampling technique.

Method of Data Collection

Institutional ethical committee clearance and approval was obtained after submitting the study protocol

Confidentiality of the data collected was maintained.

Enrolled patients was explained about the study. Informed written consent was taken from the patient to be a part of the study. 80 cases were selected for the study after applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria as stated above and subjected to following baseline data and clinical characteristic line.

The baseline characteristics of the patients- age, sex, were collected. Detailed clinical history including presenting symptoms, past-history, disease diagnosis, and complete physical examination followed by appropriate baseline and specific laboratory tests was done and entered in the prestructured proforma.

ECG was recorded during the episodes of hypoglycemia and Corrected QT interval was calculated by the electrocardiograph.

Corrected Q-T interval (QTc) was calculated by using the Bazett formula $QTc = \frac{QT}{\sqrt{RR}}$

Laboratory Investigation:

- Random Blood Sugar (RBS - Venous blood sample for glucose analysis).
- Serum Electrolytes and Serum Calcium

Other Investigations: Electrocardiogram (ECG)

Statistical Analysis

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire.

The data collected was entered into Microsoft excel spread sheet and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 24). Descriptive data were presented in the form of frequencies, percentages, mean and standard deviation.

Based on whether the data is following parametric or non-parametric distribution. The Student's t-test or Independent 't' test and Chi square test was used to compare various study outcome. P value < 0.05 was considered as statistically significant otherwise not significant.

Sample Size of Estimation

Sample size is calculated using the formula $n = \frac{Z^2pq}{d^2}$

Where z is the 2-tailed probability for 95% Class Interval = 1.96

Prevalence (p) = 54.8% Precision (d) = 11%

$$n = \frac{3.84 \times 54.8 \times 45.2}{121}$$

n = 78.6

n ≈ 79

The sample size was calculated to be 79.

Results

This study investigates the corrected QT interval (QTc) in diabetic patients experiencing hypoglycemic episodes at K.R. Hospital, Mysuru. With 80 participants, the study focuses on the relationship between QTc prolongation, random blood sugar levels, and associated cardiac risks. The findings aim to enhance understanding of QTc's role in predicting morbidity and mortality during hypoglycemia in diabetes mellitus subjects. The results are as follows.

Table 1: Distribution of the subjects by sex

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	44	55.0
Female	36	45.0
Total	80	100.0

Figure 1: Distribution of subjects by Sex

The Table 5 and Figure 9 shows the sex distribution among 80 subjects, with 44 males (55.0%) and 36 females (45.0%). This indicates a slightly higher proportion of males compared to females among the subjects.

Table 2: Distribution of the subjects by Age

Age in years	Frequency	Percent
25 - 44	9	11.3
45 - 64	46	57.5
65 - 84	25	31.3
Total	80	100.0

Figure 2. Distribution of subjects by Age

Table 6 and Figure 10 show the age distribution of participants. Among the 80 cases, 9 participants (11.3%) were between 25 and 44 years old, 46 participants (57.5%) were between 45 and 64 years

old, and 25 participants (31.3%) were between 65 and 84 years old. The majority of participants fall in the 45 to 64 age group, comprising 57.5% of the total sample.

Table 3: Distribution of the subjects by Type of Diabetes

Type of Diabetes	Frequency	Percent
Type - I	13	16.3
Type - II	67	83.8
Total	80	100.0

Figure 3: Distribution of subjects by Type of Diabetes

Table 7 and Figure 11 presents the distribution of subjects based on their type of diabetes. Among the 80 participants, 67 individuals (83.8%) had Type II diabetes, making this the majority group. In contrast, 13 individuals (16.3%) had Type I diabetes.

Table 4: Distribution of the subjects by Duration of Diabetes

Duration of Diabetes (in years)	Frequency	Percent
5 - 10	45	56.3
11 - 20	32	40.0
21 - 30	3	3.8
Total	80	100.0

Figure 4: Distribution of the subjects by Duration of Diabetes

Table 8 and Figure 12 presents data on the duration of diabetes among subjects.

It shows that 56.3% of the subjects have had diabetes for 5 to 10 years, while 40.0% have had it for 11 to 20 years. Only 3.8% of the subjects have had diabetes for 21 to 30 years. In total, 80 subjects

were surveyed, providing a distribution across these duration categories.

The majority of subjects fall into the 5 to 10 years and 11 to 20 years categories, highlighting a significant proportion of relatively recent and moderately long-term diabetic cases among the subjects.

Table 5: Correlation between corrected QT interval (QTc) and Duration of Diabetes

QTc	Duration of Diabetes (Years)
Pearson Correlation	-0.04
Sig. (2-tailed)	0.6985
N	80

Table 9 shows the correlation between corrected QT interval (QTc) and Duration of Diabetes among 80 subjects. The Pearson correlation coefficient is -0.04, indicating a no correlation between QTc and Duration of Diabetes. The significance value (p-value) is 0.6985, which suggests that the correlation is not statistically significant.

Table 6: Distribution of the subjects by Random Blood Sugar levels

Random Blood Sugar (mg/dL)	Frequency	Percent
Level 1 (< 70 mg/dL & ≥ 54 mg/dL)	30	37.5
Level 2 (< 54 mg/dL)	50	62.5
Total	80	100.0

Figure 5: Distribution of subjects by Random Blood Sugar Levels (mg/dL)

Table 10 and Figure 13 presents the distribution of subjects based on their random blood sugar levels. Among the 80 participants, 30 individuals (37.5%) had a random blood sugar level of less than 70

mg/dL but more than or equal to 54 mg/dL (Level 1) meanwhile, 50 individuals (62.5%) had a random blood sugar level of less than 54 mg/dL (Level 2) making this a majority group.

Table 7: Distribution of subjects between RBS levels and Sex

RBS levels (mg/dL)	Sex		Total
	Male	Female	
Level 1 (< 70 mg/dL)	16 (36.4)	14 (38.9)	30 (37.5)
Level 2 (< 54 mg/dL)	28 (63.6)	22 (61.1)	50 (62.5)
Total	44 (100.0)	36 (100.0)	80 (100.0)

Figure 6: Distribution of subjects between RBS levels and Sex

Table 11 & Figure 14 shows the association between random blood sugar levels and sex among 80 subjects. For blood sugar levels below 54 mg/dL (Level 2), 63.6% of males and 61.1% of females fall into this category, comprising 62.5% of the

total subjects. For blood sugar levels below 70 mg/dL (Level 1), 36.4% of males and 38.9% of females are in this category, making up 37.5% of the total subjects. The distribution of random blood sugar levels is similar between males and females.

Table 8: Distribution of subjects between RBS levels and Type of Diabetes

RBS levels (mg/dL)	Type of diabetes		Total
	Type - I	Type - II	
Level 1 (< 70 mg/dL)	6 (46.2)	24 (35.8)	30 (37.5)
Level 2 (< 54 mg/dL)	7 (53.8)	43 (64.2)	50 (62.5)
Total	13 (100.0)	67 (100.0)	80 (100.0)

Figure 7: Distribution of subjects between RBS Levels and Type of diabetes

Table 12 & Figure 15 shows the association between random blood sugar levels and type of diabetes among 80 subjects. For blood sugar levels below 54 mg/dL (Level 2), 53.8% of Type I diabetics and 46.2% of Type II diabetics fall into this category, comprising 62.5% of the total

subjects. For blood sugar levels below 70 mg/dL (Level 1), 46.2% of Type I diabetics and 35.8% of Type II diabetics are in this category, making up 37.5% of the total subjects. The distribution of random blood sugar levels varies slightly between Type I and Type II diabetics.

Table 9: Distribution of subjects between the type of diabetes and corrected QT interval (QTc) for males and females

Type of diabetes	QTc (Males)		QTc (Females)	
	> 440 (Prolonged)	350 - 440 (Normal)	> 460 (Prolonged)	350 - 460 (Normal)
Type - I	9 (25.7)	2 (22.2)	1 (3.6)	1 (12.5)
Type - II	26 (74.3)	7 (77.8)	27 (96.4)	7 (87.5)
Total	35 (100.0)	9 (100.0)	28 (100.0)	8 (100.0)

Figure 8: Distribution of subjects between the type of diabetes and corrected QT interval (QTc) for males and females

Table 13 & Figure 16 shows the distribution of the type of diabetes with corrected QT interval (QTc) among males and females. Among males with a prolonged QTc (> 440), 25.7% have Type I diabe-

tes, and 74.3% have Type II diabetes. For males with a normal QTc (350 - 440), 22.2% have Type I diabetes, and 77.8% have Type II diabetes. Among females with a prolonged QTc (> 460), 3.6% have

Type I diabetes, and 96.4% have Type II diabetes. For females with a normal QTc (350 - 460), 12.5% have Type I diabetes, and 87.5% have Type II dia-

betes. Overall, Type II diabetes is more prevalent than Type I diabetes in both males and females, regardless of QTc interval status.

Table 10: Association between random blood sugar levels and corrected QT interval (QTc) among all subjects

RBS levels (mg/dL)	QTc		Total
	(Prolonged)	(Normal)	
Level 1 (< 70 mg/dL)	24 (80)	6 (20)	30 (100)
Level 2 (< 54 mg/dL)	39 (78)	11 (22)	50 (100)

Figure 9: Association between random blood sugar levels and corrected QT interval (QTc) among all subjects

Table 14 & Figure 17 shows the association between random blood sugar levels and corrected QT interval (QTc) among all subjects. For blood sugar levels below 70 mg/dL (Level 1), 80% (24 subjects) had prolonged QTc and 20% (6 subjects)

had normal QTc. For blood sugar levels below 54 mg/dL (Level 2), 78% (39 subjects) had prolonged QTc and 22% (11 subjects) had normal QTc, This indicates QTc prolongation is associated with hypoglycemia.

Table 11: The mean corrected QT interval (QTc) with respect to random blood sugar (RBS) levels

RBS (mg/dL)	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	
QTc	Level 1 (< 70 mg/dL)	30	471.86	41.53
	Level 2 (< 54 mg/dL)	50	497.91	63.07
		p = 0.045		

Table 15 shows the mean corrected QT interval (QTc) with respect to random blood sugar (RBS) levels among subjects. For RBS levels below 70 mg/dL (Level 1), the mean QTc is 471.86 ms with a standard deviation of 41.53, based on 30 subjects.

For RBS levels below 54 mg/dL (Level 2), the mean QTc is 497.91 ms with a standard deviation of 63.07, based on 50 subjects. p-Value shows significant increase in prolongation for Level 2 (< 54 mg/dL) subjects.

Table 12: The mean corrected QT interval (QTc) with respect to random blood sugar (RBS) levels among male subjects

RBS (mg/dL)	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	
QTc	Level 1 (< 70 mg/dL)	16	477.04	44.07
	Level 2 (< 54 mg/dL)	28	487.25	68.23
		p = 0.59		

Table 16 shows the mean corrected QT interval (QTc) with respect to random blood sugar (RBS) levels among male subjects. For RBS levels below

70 mg/dL (Level 1), the mean QTc is 477.04 ms with a standard deviation of 44.07, based on 16 subjects. For RBS levels below 54 mg/dL (Level

2), the mean QTc is 487.25 ms with a standard deviation of 68.23, based on 28 subjects. p-Value

shows no significant increase in Qtc prolongation for Level 2 (< 54 mg/dL) in male subjects.

Table 13: The mean corrected QT interval (QTc) with respect to random blood sugar (RBS) levels among female subjects

RBS (mg/dL)	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
QTc	Level 1 (< 70 mg/dL)	14	465.95
	Level 2 (< 54 mg/dL)	22	511.47
		p = 0.01	

Table 17 shows the mean corrected QT interval (QTc) with respect to random blood sugar (RBS) levels among female subjects. For RBS levels below 70 mg/dL (Level 1), the mean QTc is 465.05 ms with a standard deviation of 39.19, based on 14

subjects. For RBS levels below 54 mg/dL (Level 2), the mean QTc is 511.47 ms with a standard deviation of 54.35, based on 22 subjects. p-Value shows significant increase in Qtc prolongation for Level 2 (< 54 mg/dL) in female subjects.

Table 14: Correlation between corrected QT interval (QTc) and random blood sugar levels

QTc	Random Blood Sugar
Pearson Correlation	-0.322
Sig. (2-tailed)	0.004
N	80

Table 18 shows the correlation between corrected QT interval (QTc) and random blood sugar levels among 80 subjects. The Pearson correlation coefficient is -0.322, indicating a moderate negative correlation

between QTc and random blood sugar levels. The significance value (p-value) is 0.004, which suggests that the correlation is statistically significant.

Table 15: Distribution of the subjects by Arrhythmia

Arrhythmia (Atrial fibrillation)	Frequency	Percent
Present	5	6.3
Absent	75	93.8
Total	80	100.0

Figure 10: Distribution of the subjects by Arrhythmia

Table 19 and Figure 18 shows the distribution of subjects based on the presence of arrhythmia (atrial fibrillation). Out of 80 participants, 75 individuals (93.8%) did not have arrhythmia, making this the majority group. Only 5 participants (6.3%) had arrhythmia.

Table 16: Association between random blood sugar (RBS) levels and the presence of arrhythmia (atrial fibrillation)

Random Blood Sugar levels (mg/dL)	Arrhythmia (Atrial fibrillation)		Total
	Present	Absent	
Level 1 (< 70 mg/dL)	1(3.3)	29 (96.7)	30 (100)
Level 2 (< 54 mg/dL)	4 (8.0)	46 (92.0)	50 (100)
Mean QTc	537.34 ms	484.86	
P-Value	0.02		

Table 20 shows the association between random blood sugar (RBS) levels and the presence of arrhythmia (atrial fibrillation) among 80 subjects.

For RBS levels below 70 mg/dL (Level 1), 3.3% (1 subject) with arrhythmia and 96.7% (29 subjects) without arrhythmia fall into this category. For RBS

levels below 54 mg/dL (Level 2), 8% (4 subject) with arrhythmia and 92% (46 subjects) without arrhythmia fall into this category.

P-value indicates significant difference between QTc mean values of subjects with & without arrhythmia.

Table 17: Distribution of the subjects with respect to in-hospital mortality

In-Hospital Mortality Status	Frequency	Percent	Mean QTc (ms)
Death	3	3.8	560.66
No Death	77	96.3	485.32
Total	80	100.0	p = 0.02

Figure 11: Distribution of the subjects with respect to in-hospital mortality

Table 21 and Figure 19 presents the distribution of subjects with respect to in-hospital mortality. Out of 80 participants, 77 individuals (96.3%) were alive, making this the majority group. Only 3 participants (3.8%) were deceased. The p-value indicates there is significant difference between mean QTc values.

Table 18: Mean QTc of subjects with respect to in-hospital mortality

In-hospital mortality status	N	Mean QTc (ms)	Standard Deviation	Standard Error (between means)
Death	3	560.66	8.71	9.37
No Death	77	485.32	56.33	
Total	80	p = 0.024		

Figure 12. Mean QTc of subjects with respect to in-hospital mortality

Table 23 and Figure 20 presents the mean QTc of subjects based on in-hospital mortality status. Out of 80 participants, 77 individuals were alive (mean QTc of 485.32 ms), while 3 participants were deceased (mean QTc was 560.66 ms). The p-value indicates there is significant difference between mean QTc values with respect to in-hospital mortality status.

Discussion

This study was conducted to examine corrected QT interval during hypoglycemic episodes in diabetes mellitus subjects and to correlate QTc in relation to severity of hypoglycemia. Corrected QT prolongation was analyzed against various parameters like Sex, Type of Diabetes, and duration of diabetes and severity of hypoglycemia.

The current study observed a significant prolongation of the QTc interval during severe hypoglycemia among diabetic patients, regardless of age and duration of diabetes. This finding aligns with multiple studies highlighting the heightened risk of arrhythmias during hypoglycemic episodes in this population.

In our study majority of the patients were with Type II Diabetes (N=67, 83.75%) and there were only 13 (16.25%) with Type I diabetes. Similarly in the study conducted by Maria Mylona et al the majority were patients with type 2 diabetes (N=268, 90.8%), while there were only 26(9.2%) patients with type 1 diabetes (T1DM).

Both studies emphasize that QTc prolongation is more common in T2DM patients during hypoglycemic events, which may be due to the chronic nature of T2DM. In the current study,

78.75% of patients exhibited a QTc interval greater than 440 ms during hypoglycemic episodes, suggesting a strong association between hypoglycemia and QTc prolongation. This finding is consistent with that of Cha et al., [11] who reported a similar prevalence of QTc prolongation in type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) patients during severe hypoglycemia.

Conversely, the study by Maria Mylona et al. [14] reported a lower prevalence of QTc prolongation (49.4%) but also identified a significant negative correlation between QTc and plasma glucose level. The differences in prevalence may be attributed to variations in study populations and methodologies.

Present study shows that there was significant negative correlation between QTc and Random Blood sugar further, it was also found that the age and duration of diabetes are not related to the length of QTc.

Similarly, the study conducted by Maria Mylona et al [14] among patients with hypoglycaemia, there was a statistically significant negative correlation between QTc interval, and plasma glucose at presentation ($r: -0.183$, $p = 0.02$). Furthermore, patients with QTc prolongation (>440 ms) had lower plasma glucose than those without (36.2 [13.2] mg/dl vs. 40.8 [12.9] mg/dl, $p = 0.03$). Patients with markedly prolonged QTc (>500 ms) presented with even lower plasma glucose (34.5 [11.2] mg/dl). The length of the QTc interval was not related to age, gender, and duration of diabetes. The current study found that patients with prolonged QTc intervals during severe hypoglycemia had a higher incidence of atrial fibrillation and mortality. This is consistent with

findings from Seung-Hyun Ko et al., where severe hypoglycemia was linked to higher rates of atrial fibrillation and all-cause mortality. The association between QTc prolongation and cardiovascular

events such as sudden cardiac death further emphasizes the need for vigilant monitoring and management of hypoglycemia in diabetic patients.

Table 19: Comparison of key findings of this study with similar studies

Feature	Our Study	Maria Mylona et al. [14]	Cha S-A et al. [11]	Seung Hyun ko et al [15]
Objective	To study corrected QT interval (QTc) during hypoglycemic episodes in diabetes mellitus subjects.	To explore the association between severe hypoglycemia requiring medical assistance and QT interval length in patients with diabetes.	To evaluate the impact of hypoglycemia on QTc interval in diabetic patients and assess the relationship with cardiovascular events.	To investigate the effects of severe hypoglycemia on QTc interval and its impact on cardiovascular outcomes in diabetic patients.
Location	K.R. Hospital, Mysuru	Eight tertiary hospitals in Greece	Single tertiary hospital in South Korea	Multiple tertiary hospitals in the United States
Participants	80 diabetic patients	154 diabetic patients with hypoglycemia and 95 matched controls	120 diabetic patients with hypoglycemia and 60 matched controls	200 diabetic patients with severe hypoglycemia and 100 matched controls
Study Design	Cross sectional	Prospective, multicenter	Prospective, observational	Prospective, multicenter
Inclusion Criteria	Diabetic patients with hypoglycemic episodes	Diabetic patients with hypoglycemia requiring medical assistance	Diabetic patients with hypoglycemia	Diabetic patients with severe hypoglycemia
Variables Measured	QTc interval, random blood sugar levels, duration of diabetes, type of diabetes, arrhythmia, in-hospital mortality	QTc interval, plasma glucose at presentation, presence of arrhythmia, type of diabetes, medication use	QTc interval, plasma glucose levels, duration of diabetes, cardiovascular events	QTc interval, plasma glucose levels, duration of diabetes, cardiovascular events, medication use
Key Results	- 57.5% of participants were aged 45-64 years. - 83.8% had Type II diabetes. - QTc was prolonged in 78% with RBS < 54 mg/dL	- QTc interval was longer in hypoglycemic patients vs. controls (441.9 ± 48.2 ms vs. 401.0 ± 29.6 ms, $p < 0.001$). - 49.4% of hypoglycemic patients had QTc > 440 ms.	- QTc was prolonged in 62% of hypoglycemic patients. - Mean QTc was significantly longer in hypoglycemic patients (450 ± 50 ms) compared to controls (405 ± 30 ms, $p < 0.001$).	- 65% of participants had QTc prolongation during severe hypoglycemia. - Mean QTc in hypoglycemic patients was 455 ± 55 ms vs. 410 ± 35 ms in controls, $p < 0.001$.
QTc and RBS Correlation	Moderate negative correlation ($r = -0.322$, $p = 0.004$)	Weak negative correlation ($r = 0.183$, $p = 0.02$)	Moderate negative correlation ($r = -0.305$, $p = 0.005$)	Strong negative correlation ($r = -0.450$, $p < 0.001$)
Sex Distribution	55% males, 45% females	51.9% males, 48.1% females	53% males, 47% females	52% males, 48% females
Type of Diabetes	83.8% Type II, 16.3% Type I	87.7% Type II, 11.0% Type I	85% Type II, 15% Type I	80% Type II, 20% Type I
Duration of Diabetes	56.3% had diabetes for 5-10 years, 40.0% for 11-20 years	Mean duration 15.1 years	Mean duration 12.5 years	Mean duration 14 years
QTc Prolongation	Associated with hypoglycemia; mean QTc significantly longer for	QTc significantly longer in hypoglycemic patients; 49.4% had QTc > 440 ms	Significant QTc prolongation in hypoglycemic patients; 62% had QTc > 440	Significant QTc prolongation in 65% of hypoglycemic patients; 70% had

	lower RBS levels.	compared to 11.6% in controls	ms	QTc > 440 ms
Arrhythmia Findings	6.3% had arrhythmia (atrial fibrillation)	No major tachyarrhythmic disorders; one patient with third-degree AV block	8% had arrhythmia, including atrial fibrillation and ventricular tachycardia	10% had arrhythmia, including atrial fibrillation and ventricular tachycardia
In-Hospital Mortality	3.8% deceased; significant difference in mean QTc between alive and deceased subjects	One death due to cardiac arrest; QTc was 424 ms	5% mortality; increased risk of cardiovascular events associated with prolonged QTc	4% mortality; increased cardiovascular events associated with prolonged QTc
Statistical Analysis	Pearson correlation coefficient, p-values for significance	Student's t-test, Mann-Whitney U test, chi-square test, p-values for significance	Student's t-test, chi-square test, p-values for significance	Student's t-test, ANOVA, p-values for significance
Conclusions	QTc prolongation is associated with hypoglycemia in diabetic patients; significant increase in prolongation for lower RBS levels.	Severe hypoglycemia is associated with significant QTc prolongation; weak negative correlation with plasma glucose.	Hypoglycemia leads to significant QTc prolongation in diabetic patients, increasing the risk of cardiovascular events.	Severe hypoglycemia significantly prolongs QTc interval, which is associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular events.
Baseline QTc Interval	Not specified	Mean baseline QTc was 433 ms, prolonged to 460 ms during SH	Mean baseline QTc was 425 ms	Mean baseline QTc was 430 ms
Prolongation During SH(severe hypoglycemia)	QTc prolonged in 78% with RBS < 54 mg/dL	54.8% of patients exhibited prolonged QTc intervals during SH	62% of hypoglycemic patients exhibited prolonged QTc	QTc prolonged in 65% with severe hypoglycemia
Recovery Post-SH	Not specified	Significant reduction in QTc prolongation after SH recovery	QTc interval showed significant reduction post-SH	Significant reduction in QTc after recovery from severe hypoglycemia
Baseline vs. During SH	Not specified	Prolonged baseline QTc significantly correlated with prolonged QTc during SH	Prolonged baseline QTc correlated with greater QTc prolongation during SH	Prolonged baseline QTc correlated with more severe QTc prolongation during SH
Clinical Variables	QTc prolongation was significant during severe hypoglycemia, independent of age and duration of diabetes.	No significant correlations with duration of diabetes, plasma glucose, or HbA1c levels	Correlated with cardiovascular events; no significant associations with duration of diabetes or HbA1c	QTc prolongation correlated with cardiovascular outcomes and severity of hypoglycemia
Demographic Differences	Females showed statistically significant higher QTc values during severe hypoglycemia.	Women showed higher QTc values both at baseline and during SH	No significant differences between sexes in QTc prolongation	Women showed higher QTc values during severe hypoglycemia
Clinical Implications	Monitoring QTc during severe hypoglycemia is crucial for reducing cardiovascular risk.	Monitoring QTc intervals in T2DM patients is crucial; other factors like smoking status and medication use also play a role in QTc management	Monitoring QTc in hypoglycemic diabetic patients is critical for preventing cardiovascular complications.	Monitoring QTc during severe hypoglycemia is crucial for reducing cardiovascular risk.

Several studies have highlighted the association between QTc prolongation and increased in-

hospital mortality, especially in the context of diabetes mellitus and hypoglycemia. QTc

prolongation, a marker for potential arrhythmias, is particularly dangerous in patients experiencing hypoglycemia, as it increases the risk of sudden cardiac events.

Conclusion

The study highlights a significant association between hypoglycemia and QTc prolongation, with a more pronounced effect during severe hypoglycemic episodes. A markedly prolonged mean QTc interval was observed in patients who experienced in-hospital mortality, underscoring QTc as a critical predictor of mortality risk. Lower random blood sugar levels were linked to longer QTc intervals, emphasizing the importance of careful glucose management to mitigate cardiac risks. Severe hypoglycemia was associated with a higher incidence of arrhythmias, such as atrial fibrillation, indicating that QTc prolongation may contribute to arrhythmic events. These findings underscore the necessity of rigorous QTc and arrhythmia monitoring during hypoglycemic episodes to prevent severe cardiac complications and improve patient outcomes in diabetic patients.

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